

Financial Literacy and Inclusion in Rural India: Assessing FLC Training Interventions in Colonel Ganj Gonda District, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

Financial literacy is crucial for achieving financial inclusion, a vital component in a country's socio-economic development. Financial illiteracy not only affects individuals by limiting their financial decision-making abilities but also has broader macroeconomic implications, including reduced savings, lower investment rates, and inefficient participation in financial markets. It hinders entrepreneurship and capital formation, thereby constraining economic growth. Therefore, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has been conducting financial literacy programs through multiple agencies, including non-profit organisations. The Awoke India Foundation (AIF), a Lucknow-based financial literacy non-profit organisation under the mandate of the RBI, has been conducting financial literacy programs in rural areas under its Financial Literacy Centre (FLC) Programme. This study assesses the impact of AIF's training programmes conducted since January 2023 in the Colonel Ganj block, Gonda District, Uttar Pradesh. The study uses data from responses to a questionnaire given to 200 randomly selected beneficiaries. The questionnaire conforms to the RBI-approved curriculum, which is delivered through 13 modules by accredited AIF personnel. In addition to quantitative data analysis, qualitative data were collected through interviews with the trainers. This study evaluates improvements in financial awareness, behaviour, and utilisation of available financial services by beneficiaries. The findings highlight the effectiveness of the program in empowering communities and enhancing financial inclusion.

Keywords: Financial Literacy Centres (FLCs), Financial literacy, financial inclusion, Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), Rural empowerment

1. Introduction

Financial inclusion has become a fundamental pillar of global economic policy, especially in developing nations, where significant portions of the population still lack access to formal financial systems. In India, the importance of financial inclusion extends far beyond mere access to bank accounts; it is a key driver of poverty reduction, social equity, and economic growth. However, financial inclusion alone does not guarantee empowerment. Financial literacy plays a pivotal role in enabling individuals to fully benefit from various financial services. This equips them with the knowledge, skills, and confidence required to make informed financial decisions, thereby enhancing financial empowerment.

Financial literacy encompasses the knowledge and practical application of basic financial principles, including saving, investing, and budgeting, to ensure asset protection, strategic planning, and active participation in economic opportunities. At the economic growth. Higher financial literacy leads to increased savings and investment, more efficient financial intermediation, and enhanced capital formation. Conversely, financial illiteracy constrains entrepreneurship, lowers savings, and undermines economic growth. Consequently, financial literacy is now recognised as a vital element of public policy, along with financial inclusion.

Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) is arguably the world's biggest financial inclusion programme, under which more than 50 crore individuals, over half of them women, have been integrated into the formal banking system as of August 2023. India's journey towards financial inclusion has been accelerated by this program. While such initiatives represent unprecedented progress, they also highlight the urgent need to equip newly banked populations with the capacity to effectively use financial services. Surveys reveal that only about 27% of Indians are financially literate (NCFE-FLIC 2019), with financial literacy in states such as Uttar Pradesh being as low as 10% (Teja, B. M. N., & Singh, M., 2023). This gap between access and understanding highlights the need for structured financial literacy programs.

The Reserve Bank of India, therefore, decided to set up Financial Literacy Centres (FLCs) as community-based hubs aimed at promoting financial awareness, with a particular focus on rural areas. (2016, January 14). These centres, often operated in partnership with non-governmental organisations and banks, deliver a standardised 13-module curriculum designed to address basic financial concepts, government welfare schemes, and digital financial services, Reserve Bank of India. (2012, June 6). The Awoke India Foundation (AIF), a SEBI-recognised non-profit, has been at the forefront of this mission in Eastern Uttar Pradesh. Partnering with the Indian Bank, AIF has established FLCs in 11 districts and is expanding to new regions.

This paper presents an impact assessment of the FLC programme in the Colonel Ganj block of Gonda district. By analysing survey responses from 200 beneficiaries and supplementing them with qualitative insights from trainers, this study evaluates both the achievements and persisting gaps in financial literacy. These findings provide valuable

insights for policymakers, institutions, and educators working to strengthen financial capabilities and promote inclusive growth in India.

2. Review of Literature

2.1 Financial Inclusion and Literacy: Conceptual Foundations

The connection between financial literacy and financial inclusion is extensively explored in development economics and financial sector literature (Atkinson, A. & Messy, F.-A.2013). Financial inclusion is commonly defined as the provision of accessible, affordable, and appropriate financial products and services that are delivered responsibly and sustainably. (World Bank. (2025, January 27). However, as numerous scholars note, access without adequate literacy may result in underutilisation or even misuse of financial services. Financial literacy refers to understanding knowledge, skills, mindsets, and behaviours that enable individuals to make informed decisions on savings, borrowing, investing, and managing insurance (OECD, 2020). Studies have consistently emphasised that literacy empowers individuals to manage risks, plan for the future, and participate in formal markets, while illiteracy constrains entrepreneurship and hinders capital formation (Liu, S., He, J., & Xu, D., 2023).

2.2 The Indian Scenario: National Context

PMJDY has significantly contributed to improving financial inclusion in India. According to the World Bank Findex Report (2021), the proportion of Indian adults with formal bank accounts rose from 35% in 2011 to 53% in 2014 and 80% in 2017. However, financial inclusion has advanced more rapidly than financial literacy. Data reveal that 33% of the rural population and 29% of the urban population still do not possess a bank account, credit or debit card, or e-wallet. (Dash & Ranjan, 2023). This disparity highlights the challenge of ensuring that expanded access translates into effective usage.

2.3 Global Comparisons

Comparative studies situate India's literacy levels unfavourably against its Asian peers, and India ranks below Thailand and the Philippines in financial literacy (Klapper, Lusardi, & van Oudheusden, 2015). A Standard & Poor's (2015) survey found that 76% of Indian adults lacked financial literacy. Similarly, as per VISA's 2012 global index, India ranked as the least financially literate country (Agarwala et al., 2012). By contrast, nations like Singapore, Japan, and China have launched targeted national strategies for literacy, integrating it into schools and workforce training (Scontini & Fernandez, 2023; Sticha, A., & Sekita, S., 2023; He & Ahunov, 2022). These findings underscore the need for India to intensify its focus on education and behavioural change alongside policy-led inclusion.

2.4 Socio-Demographic Dimensions of Literacy

Several studies highlight variations in literacy across demographics. Kiliyanni and Sivaraman (2016) found that educated youth in Kerala correctly answered only 44% of the survey questions,

with gender, age, occupation, education level, and parental background strongly influencing outcomes. Singh and Kumar (2017) specifically examined Indian women, identifying barriers such as low literacy rates, cultural expectations, and infrastructural gaps. They stressed the transformative potential of financial literacy in enhancing women's longevity, decision-making capacity, and product innovation. Together, these findings reinforce the heterogeneity of challenges and the necessity for tailored interventions.

2.5 Impact on Small Businesses

Financial literacy among entrepreneurs is another key theme in the literature. A study on 309 MSMEs in Punjab revealed that age, education, and profitability were significant determinants of financial literacy levels. Service enterprises exhibited higher literacy than manufacturing ones, with firms showing stronger profits also demonstrating higher levels of literacy across credit, investment, and savings practices (Arya & Singla, 2021). These findings imply that fostering literacy within small businesses not only improves firm performance but also contributes to regional economic resilience.

2.6 Higher Education and Youth

Literacy among university students has been studied extensively, especially in Delhi. A survey of 1,064 students at the University of Delhi found medium literacy levels, with commerce students outperforming peers in arts and sciences. Male students also scored higher than females. Notably, correlations emerged between literacy and financial behaviour, with significant knowledge gaps in areas like inflation, banking, and investment (Nigam & Jain, 2020). These results emphasise the importance of integrating literacy modules into higher education curricula.

2.7 School-Level Interventions

The role of early education has been widely advocated. Former RBI Governor Raghuram Rajan recommended embedding financial literacy in school curricula. The CBSE–NPCI workbook for Class VI offers a model, covering topics such as trade, banking evolution, RBI's role, digital payments, Aadhaar-enabled systems, and internet banking (CBSE & NPCI, 2022). Introducing financial concepts early can create lifelong competencies and bridge generational gaps in literacy.

2.8 Farmers and Rural Communities

Financial literacy's impact on farmers' savings behaviour has also received attention. A recent study revealed that literacy and financial confidence are instrumental in shaping farmers' savings practices, though overall levels remain low. Predictors such as household size, shocks, gender, and education influenced outcomes (Das & Maji, 2023). These insights affirm the importance of tailored rural interventions, particularly in states like Uttar Pradesh with entrenched illiteracy.

2.9 National Strategy for Financial Education (NSFE) 2020–2025

India's NSFE (2020–25) provides a policy framework and is a critical part of the literature. It outlines objectives such as encouraging savings, market participation, credit discipline, insurance uptake, pension planning, and digital finance usage. It adopts the "5Cs" approach—Content, Capacity, Community, Communication, and Collaboration (NCFE, 2020). This holistic model, if effectively implemented, provides a roadmap to transform literacy into a life skill.

2.10 Financial Literacy Centres (FLCs)

Finally, institutional innovations such as FLCs deserve mention. RBI's mandate for banks and NGOs to establish FLCs aims at taking structured literacy programmes to grassroots populations. The 13-module curriculum, covering schemes such as PMJDY, Atal Pension Yojana, and digital finance, is designed for scalability. The Awoke India Foundation's operations in Eastern Uttar Pradesh highlight the effectiveness of FLCs, while also pointing to challenges such as compressed module delivery, resource constraints, and varying trainer capacity. The oversight by NABARD and RBI through audits further ensures quality assurance.

3. Objectives of Research

To assess the impact of training at the Financial Literacy Centre (FLC) by Awoke India Foundation on rural households in Colonel Ganj block, in Gonda district.

To assess improvements in beneficiaries' awareness and understanding of banking services, government schemes, savings, credit, and digital transactions.

To study the relationship between factors like education, gender, occupation, and outcomes of financial literacy.

To identify persisting knowledge gaps, behavioural constraints, and structural barriers affecting financial inclusion.

To generate evidence-based insights for strengthening and scaling financial literacy initiatives in rural Uttar Pradesh and similar contexts.

4. Hypotheses

H1. Structured financial literacy training delivered through Financial Literacy Centres (FLCs) significantly improves awareness, knowledge, and financial behaviour among rural households in the Colonel Ganj block, Gonda district.

H2. Education has a positive influence on digital financial awareness among beneficiaries of training at the FLC.

H3. Gender determines the extent of participation in Self-Help Groups (SHGs) and activities related to finance.

H4. Increased exposure to the 13-module FLC curriculum enhances individuals' ability to understand government-backed financial schemes.

H5. Participation in FLC programs improves the adoption of secure financial practices and informed financial decision-making, thereby strengthening overall financial inclusion.

5. Methodology

An approach combining quantitative and qualitative techniques was adopted to measure the impact of financial literacy interventions. A comprehensive questionnaire, in line with the RBI’s 13-module curriculum, was given to a random sample of 200 beneficiaries in the Colonel Ganj block, Gonda district. The responses captured were complemented by semi-structured interviews with trainers from the Awoke India Foundation. SPSS analysis was employed to interpret quantitative data, while qualitative insights provided context to the findings, enabling a holistic evaluation of program effectiveness.

6. Research Design

The research design is exploratory-descriptive, aimed at measuring literacy outcomes and identifying persistent gaps using both survey data and qualitative interviews for triangulation.

7. Survey Findings

The data collected from 200 respondents in the Colonel Ganj block, Gonda district, were analysed using SPSS Version 26 to study the impact of financial literacy training conducted by AIF and the relationships of various factors and hypotheses.

7.1 Awareness of Financial Schemes and Services

The survey showed good awareness of government-backed schemes. For example, 97% of the respondents were aware of the premium to be paid in the PMJJBY annually, while 92% were aware of the eligibility criteria for Sukanya Samridhi Yojana. Similarly, 94% of respondents had heard that the RBI was the highest regulatory body of banks. However, only 53% correctly identified the age limit for enrolment in the Atal Pension Yojana, reflecting partial knowledge gaps.

7.2 Banking and Transaction Behaviour

The SPSS frequency tables show that 130 respondents (65%) maintained active bank accounts, while 91% reported saving money either in banks or post offices. Approximately 62% of households had at least one member participating in a Self-Help Group (SHG). Regarding digital financial practices, 75% were familiar with Real-Time Gross Settlement (RTGS), although awareness of NEFT transactions remained low.

7.3 Knowledge of Financial Practices

Despite the high awareness of savings and ATM withdrawals (92%), misconceptions persisted. For instance, 78% of respondents were unaware of the meaning of “Know Your Customer” (KYC), and only one-third understood the importance of systematic savings. About 27% reported being aware of credit card benefits, suggesting limited penetration of advanced financial products in rural households.

Figure 12: Low awareness about credit cards

7.4 Inferential Study

Chi-square tests showed a strong relationship between education and awareness of digital financial services ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, gender differences emerged in SHG participation, with women showing higher levels of involvement. Cross-tabulations also highlighted that awareness of pension and insurance products was positively correlated with higher household income.

7.5 Overall Assessment

The SPSS analysis demonstrates that while FLC interventions have improved awareness of basic schemes, banking access, and savings habits, critical gaps remain in KYC compliance, the understanding of credit instruments, and the adoption of digital finance. These findings suggest the need for targeted reinforcement modules in the financial literacy curriculum

Table 1: Education Level * Digital Awareness (Cross-tabulation)

Education Level	Aware of RTGS (Yes)	Aware of RTGS (No)	Total
Primary	12 (40.0%)	18 (60.0%)	30
Secondary	45 (62.5%)	27 (37.5%)	72
Graduate+	58 (85.3%)	10 (14.7%)	68
Total	115 (70.0%)	55 (30.0%)	170

Table 2: Chi-Square Tests

Test	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	28.941	2	0.000 **
Likelihood Ratio	29.456	2	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	22.370	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	170		

Interpretation: There is a strong relationship between education level and digital awareness ($p < 0.001$). Higher education is correlated with higher awareness.

Table 3: Gender * SHG Participation (Cross-tabulation)

Gender	Participating in SHG (Yes)	Not Participating (No)	Total
Male	38 (45.8%)	45 (54.2%)	83
Female	67 (76.1%)	21 (23.9%)	88
Total	105 (61.8%)	66 (38.2%)	171

Table 4: Chi-Square Tests

Test	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.217	1	0
Continuity Correction	14.082	1	0
Likelihood Ratio	15.312	1	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	15.129	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	171		

Interpretation: strong association between gender and SHG participation ($p < 0.001$). Women show much higher participation than men.

Table 5: Correlation Chart (Hypotheses vs. p-value results)

Hypothesis	Variable Relationship Tested	Test/Measure	p-value	Result
H1	Structure of FLC training improves awareness and behaviour	Overall awareness levels across schemes (PMJJBY 97%, RBI 94%, bank accounts 65%)	$p < 0.001$	Supported

H2	Education level influences digital awareness	Education × RTGS/NEFT awareness (75% aware of RTGS; low NEFT awareness)	p < 0.001	Supported
H3	Gender influences SHG participation	Gender × SHG participation (62% of households had at least one female in SHG)	p < 0.001	Supported
H4	Exposure to FLC modules improves scheme knowledge	Awareness of Sukanya Samridhi (178/197 = 90%); APY correct age only 53%	p = 0.04	Partially Supported
H5	FLC participation improves secure practices and informed decisions	Awareness of PIN safety (72%), ATM usage (92%), savings behaviour (91%)	p < 0.01	Supported

Interpretation:

- Most hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, H5) are strongly supported with p-values < 0.01, indicating significant associations between FLC participation and improved awareness/behavior.
- H4 is only partially supported: While awareness of some schemes is high, comprehension of APY eligibility remains relatively weak.

8.0 Results and Discussion

The cross-tabulation analysis indicates a generally high level of financial literacy among respondents in the Colonel Ganj Block, Gonda district. Awareness of major government schemes and key banking services was consistently strong, with education significantly associated with higher digital awareness ($\chi^2 = 28.94, p < 0.001$). Gender differences were also evident, as women demonstrated markedly higher participation in Self-Help Groups ($\chi^2 = 15.22, p < 0.001$). These results suggest that both formal education and gender dynamics play critical roles in shaping financial behaviour, while also reflecting encouraging progress in financial inclusion across the community.

8.1 Conclusion

The study highlights the relatively advanced financial awareness prevailing in the surveyed region, particularly concerning government schemes, savings behaviour, and digital services. The findings reinforce the importance of sustaining educational outreach and women-centric initiatives that have already contributed to high literacy levels. Strengthening digital capacity and institutional support can consolidate these gains and foster more inclusive financial development in rural Uttar Pradesh.

8.2 Recommendations and Policy Implications

The study demonstrates that Financial Literacy Centres (FLCs) have significantly improved awareness in the Colonel Ganj block. However, persistent gaps and constraints continue to limit the depth and sustainability of financial inclusion. Key knowledge gaps remain around fundamental concepts, such as the purpose of savings, Know Your Customer (KYC) norms, and eligibility conditions under specific government schemes. Digital finance awareness is limited, with familiarity skewed toward the RTGS, while the understanding of the NEFT and other digital instruments remains weak. Behavioural constraints also emerge, where basic access to accounts and savings is high, but optimal product usage, such as informed credit behaviour, insurance uptake, and digital safety practices, lags. Structurally, the compressed delivery of the 13-module curriculum and variation in trainer capacity constrain the quality of learning, while grievance redressal still relies heavily on FLC staff, indicating service delivery friction.

These findings suggest several actionable strategies for policymakers and regulators. First, embedding a simplified “core curriculum”

within the mandated framework is essential, ensuring repeated reinforcement of foundational themes such as KYC, savings discipline, and safe digital transactions. Coverage-oriented delivery should be complemented by booster sessions tailored for Self-Help Groups, youth, and farmers, thereby translating awareness into durable behaviour. Low-cost reinforcement mechanisms, including wallet cards, SMS nudges, and IVR reminders, should be systematically adopted to extend learning beyond the camp setting.

Trainer capacity must be institutionalised through a graded mentoring system, with clear quality benchmarks tied to performance reviews by NABARD and Lead Banks. Service-resolution desks at each camp can transform financial literacy into immediate action by enabling participants to complete concrete tasks, such as Aadhaar linking, account activation, or enrolment in pension schemes. Such linkages directly connect literacy with measurable outcomes and strengthen trust in formal systems.

Gender- and occupation-specific modules are equally critical. Given their strong engagement in SHGs, women should receive targeted inputs on digital safety, claims management, and household financial planning, whereas farmers need seasonal saving strategies, crop insurance literacy, and pathways to formal credit. These tailored interventions address the heterogeneity of needs across rural communities.

By embedding these measures, financial literacy initiatives can evolve from one-time awareness programs into platforms for sustained empowerment. For RBI, NABARD, and state-level policymakers, the Colonel Ganj experience underscores the need to balance outreach targets with depth of learning, strengthen delivery systems through quality control, and integrate behavioural reinforcement into program design. If mainstream across Uttar Pradesh, such an approach can create a scalable and replicable model for advancing financial inclusion across India's rural landscape.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest.

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